

UrbanAIR

Brand Guidelines

Welcome to UrbanAIR brand book

This brand book contains the foundations of the UrbanAIR project's positioning. It has been created to reflect our approach and to drive awareness around the organisation. In the following pages you will find information on how to apply the visual identity consistently, effectively and efficiently.

The principles of our communication

UrbanAIR's visual communication is designed to be **clear, impactful, and cohesive**, reinforcing our mission for cleaner urban environments. We prioritise **simplicity and readability**, using a well-structured hierarchy in typography, consistent color schemes, and data-driven visuals. Our designs embrace **modern, dynamic layouts** that enhance engagement while maintaining a **professional and scientific tone**. Icons, infographics, and real-world imagery are key tools in making complex information accessible, ensuring that every visual element strengthens our message of innovation, sustainability, and urban resilience.

Brand Guidelines

LOGOTYPE

Logotype anatomy

Logotype anatomy

Color negative logotype

Logotype on dark background

Color usage | Alternative colors

Color usage | Alternative colors

Logo Mark | Symbol/icon for social media, favicon and other applications

Version on white

Version on dark

Clearspace and minimum size

Exclusion zone (clearspace)

The logo's and icon's exclusion zones are equal to the height of the wordmark's capital letter

Minimum print size

Minimum digital size

Clearspace and minimum size

Exclusion zone (clearspace)

The logo's and icon's exclusion zones are equal to the height of the wordmark's capital letter

Minimum print size

30mm

Minimum digital size

90px

Incorrect use

Always protect the integrity and appearance of our logotype. No modification or reinterpretation of the logo should occur as per the illustrated examples.

DO NOT use colors on logo that are not approved

DO NOT blend or add any drop shadow effect on logo

DO NOT stretch logo in any way

DO NOT flip any part of logo horizontally or vertically

DO NOT create outline borders around logo or outline logo

DO NOT change position or size of any part of logo

Brand Elements
THE COLORS

Color palette

Logo use against backgrounds

DO'S

DONT'S

Brand Elements

LOGO APPLICATIONS

Logo applications

UrbanAIR

**URBAN simulation
for AIR quality
and heat resilience
strategies**

 **Funded by
the European Union**

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urbanair-project.eu

UrbanAIR

**UrbanAIR
launches
to help cities
stay cool &
breathe
cleaner air.**

February 2025 | 1st Press Release

**Guiding Cities
Towards a Smarter,
Climate-Resilient Future**

urbanair-project.eu

Logo applications

The typography

Proposed typeface A

Montserrat is a geometric sans-serif typeface designed by Argentine graphic designer Julieta Ulanovsky and released in 2011. It was inspired by posters, signs and painted windows from the first half of the twentieth century, seen in the historic Montserrat neighbourhood of Buenos Aires.

<https://fonts.google.com/specimen/Montserrat>

Aa

Montserrat

Montserrat Regular

Montserrat Italic

Montserrat Bold

Montserrat Bold Italic

A B C D E F G H I J K L M N O P Q R S T U V W

X Y Z 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 0 ! @ # \$ % ^ & * ()

The typography

Proposed typeface B

Play is a minimalistic sans serif typeface designed by Jonas Hecksher during his time as Type Director of Playtype Type Foundry. All letters in Play derive from the 'O' – square and circular at the same time. Play is designed with large, open counters, ample lowercase x-heights and a corporate, yet friendly appearance. The combination of these qualities give Play both a high legibility and readability.

<https://fonts.google.com/specimen/Play?query=play>

Aa

Play Regular
Play Bold

Play

A B C D E F G H I J K L M N O P Q R S T U V W

X Y Z 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 0 ! @ # \$ % ^ & * ()

Thank you!

